

Maximization of Entropy Density With Respect to the Distribution in Generalized Statistical Mechanics

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For usual statistical mechanics, one may maximize Shannon's entropy $-f \ln(f)$ with respect to the constraint $-1/T (e-u) f$, where u is the chemical potential, to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. This procedure is essentially equivalent to a scattering approach in which $\ln(f) = -(e-u)/T$ ((1)) at equilibrium. In generalized statistical mechanics (1), one may generalize ((1)) to $\ln(g(f)) = -(e-u)/T$ ((2)). For the Fermi-Dirac case, $g=f/(1-f)$ and for the Bose Einstein case $g=f/(1+f)$ as two examples. One may also "create" an entropy density, called Kaniadakis entropy, by integrating $\ln(g(f))$ over df . Then, when one takes the derivative with respect to f , one receives back $\ln(g(f))$ which is equated to $-d/df (e-u)f/T$, in other words ((2)). It was shown in a previous note (2) that Kaniadakis entropy used in $E-TS+uN$ leads to \ln of the grand canonical partition function. Taking d/db where $b=1/T$ yields the average energy.

In this note, we wish to (A) to show that in the case of converting Kaniadakis entropy to \ln of the grand partition function, one moves from d/df to d/db ($b=1/T$) because the change d/df is related to a change in the equilibrium value of f with respect to a change in T . This, it seems, is a very restricted type of variation in f . We also wish to (B) consider what seem to be issues with a generalized variation of entropy density with respect to f and g .

Scattering Theory

We have argued in previous notes, that one may obtain the equilibrium distribution for regular and generalized statistical mechanics by considering a time reversal elastic scattering balance. Such an approach does not use counting scenarios, entropy or partition functions. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case:

$f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ ((3a)) and $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((3b)) For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein

cases: $f(e_1)[1-/+(e_3)] f(e_2)[1-/+(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1-/+(e_1)] f(e_4)[1-/+(e_2)]$ ((4a)) and ((3b)) still holds.

For the equilibrium case, ((4a)) implies: $\ln\{ f(e_i)/[1-/+(e_i)]\} = -(e_i-u)/T$ ((5)) where u is the chemical potential. (One takes \ln of ((4a)) and equates to ((3b)) with u/T added.)

Kaniadakis (1) writes ((5)) in a general way, namely: $\ln(k(f)) = -(e_i-u)/T$ ((6)).

For the MB case, k =the identity function, while for fermions $k(f)=f/(1-f)$ etc. Kaniadakis goes on to create a Fokker-Planck equation and obtain ((5)) after some algebra. We suggest ((5)) appears immediately by considering a two body scattering balance and elastic collisions.

A point we wish to raise is that in writing ((5)) or ((6)), one has made use of an equilibrium property, especially for the FD and BE cases. As can be seen from ((4a)), it is only in the equilibrium case one may use an “=” sign. Then, one is able to divide say $[1-f(e_1)]$ from the RHS of ((4a)) and associate it with $f(e_1)$ on the LHS. Thus, “g” is really an equilibrium quantity. If one did not have equilibrium, then ((4a)) would become:

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] \text{ not equal } f(e_3) [1-f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)] \quad ((7))$$

There would, it seems, not be justification to use $f(e_i)/[1-f(e_i)]$, an equilibrium result, in a “variational” method. Using “g” would imply a “special” kind of variation, perhaps from one T value to another, because the g form $f(e_i)/[1-f(e_i)] = f((e-u)/T) / [1-f((e-u)/T)]$ would hold for both.

Kaniadakis Entropy

In (1), an entropy density S_d is created: $S_d = - \int df \ln(g(f))$. ((8))

If one uses FD or BE cases ((4a)), S_d yields results compatible with those in statistical mechanics texts (3). These are obtained from factorial considerations. In (2), it was shown that this is a general situation applying to more than the FD or BD cases.

A main idea of the Kaniadakis S_d ((8)) is that if one varies it with respect to f i.e. d/df subject to the constraint $-f(e_i-u)/T$ one obtains: $\ln(g(f)) = - (e_i-u)/T$ which may be solved for f . ((9)) This is no surprise because in ((8)) one integrates over df and then takes d/df . These are inverse operations which return $g(f)$. What is interesting, however, is that if one takes the entropy from ((8)) and uses it in:

$E-TS + uN$ ((9)) one obtains $\ln(\text{Grand Canonical Partition Function})$.

Thus, an “extremization process” or variation of S_d ((8)) with respect to a constraint yields an equation which may be solved for f , but using S_d to calculate \ln of the Grand Canonical Partition function yields: average E and average N if one takes derivatives with respect to d/db ($b=1/T$) or d/dz ($z = \exp(u/T)$).

It seems it would be good to consider the link between these two sets of derivatives, namely d/df and d/db for example.

Consider as in (2) and (3) $S_d = f \ln(g) + B(f)$ where $\ln(g) = (e-u)/T$

(In other words, S_d is $f((e-u)/T) + B(f)$. See (3) page 184).

It was shown in (2) that $f d/df \ln(g) + dB/df = 0$. This follows from the variational approach, namely:

$$d/d_f S_d = (e-u)/T + dB/d_f + f d \ln(g)/d_f. \quad ((10))$$

$g(f)$, but at equilibrium f is a function of $(e-u)/T$. Thus, consider multiplying ((10)) by df/db where $b=1/T$ and treating $z=\exp(u/T)$ as an independent variable. Then:

$$f [d/d_f \ln(g)] df/db + dB/d_f df/db = 0 \quad ((11))$$

This may be rewritten as: $f d/db \ln(g) + dB/db = 0$ ((12)), but $\ln(g) = -b(e-u) = -be + \ln(z)$ so

$$- \int e^i f + dB/db = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad dB/db = \int e^i f \quad ((12))$$

((12)) is the grand canonical partition function result, so $B = \ln[\text{Grand partition function}]$.

It should be pointed out, however, that in the above, the variation of “ f ” is a “special” one. At first one uses d/d_f on S_d in a variational approach. The variational approach is supposed to consider all deviations from the function f , not just a “special” one resulting from the change T . It seems, however, that implicitly this is the only variation of f that occurs, thus S_d Kaniadakis becomes linked to \ln of the grand canonical partition function which is related to derivatives of d/db ($b=1/T$) or d/dz ($z=\exp(bu)$).

Further Issues with the Variational Approach

We wish to consider other issues with the variational approach. From the above, it is known the variation of Kaniadakis entropy density $S_d = \int df \ln(g)$ subject to the Lagrange multiplier $1/T(e-u) f$ yields: $\ln(g) = -1/T(e-u)$. ((12))

It is also known from ((6)) that $g(f) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$. Thus, one can establish a variational approach identical to that of Jaynes, namely:

$$d/d_g \{ -g \ln(g) + 1/T(e-u) g \} = 0 \quad ((13))$$

Formally, this yields $\ln(g) = -1/T(e-u)$, but the constraint $1/T(e-u) g$ does not seem to arise physically in a simple way. If one tries to use $1/T(e-u) f$ as the constraint in ((13)), one does not obtain the same result.

It has been argued that ((12)) is already unusual because $\ln(g)$ as a function of f really represents an “equilibrium” situation. For example, for fermions $g=f/(1-f)$. One would not even use such a form if one did not have “equilibrium”. The variational approach, however, should not impose “equilibrium forms” it seems.

In ((13)), one varies “ g ”. g is a function of f , but its known form holds only at equilibrium. For example, for fermions $g=f/(1-f)$, but only at equilibrium. In ((13)), one has no idea of the

functional form of $g(f)$ on f and so obtains a general result of $g = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$ which holds for all cases, fermions, bosons and more general situations.

If one assumes $g(f)$, ((13)) may be varied with respect to f i.e.:

$d/df \{ g(f) \ln(g(f)) + 1/T (e-u) g \} = 0$ or $1 + \ln(g) + 1/T(e-u) = 0$ This also yields a correct result, however,

$d/df \{ g(f) \ln(g(f) + 1/T (e-u) f \} = 0$ ((14)) does not yield the correct result even though the constraint is physical.

To evaluate ((14)), one needs to know the form of $g(f)$ even away from equilibrium. Knowledge of $g(f)$ from scattering, e.g. $g = f/(1-f)$ for fermions only holds at equilibrium. It seems that when dealing with g i.e. scattering, one needs to know why one uses an entropy density in the first place. In general, Shannon's entropy form: $-g \ln(g)$ comes from $\ln(g!)$ for large g . Thus, $g(e_i)$ represents the number of scatterings of a particle with e_i . One does not need to know $f(e_i)$. One wants to assign $g(e_i)$ values so that $M! / [g(e_1)! g(e_2)! \dots]$ is a maximum. Thus, it seems one must be careful using the extremum procedure. In all cases, $g(e_i) = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$. One then needs to use the "physics" at equilibrium (e.g. time reversal scattering balance) to link g to f , $f(e_i)$ being the number of particles with energy e_i .

In addition, we have argued the physics is associated with energy conservation in a collision. The constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{ave}$ represents the total energy in the system, but does not really enforce conservation of energy in a collision. Thus, using $\sum_i f(e_i)$ is not an appropriate constraint for $-g \ln(g)$ which describes scattering of particles. One needs to ensure that the scattering $g(e_i)$ is linked to $(e-u)/T$. There is no need for a factor of dg/df in the scattering scheme. $g(e_i)$ is the probability for a particle with e_i to scatter and the scattering reaction must conserve energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue one may obtain $f(e_i)$ from a time reversal scattering approach which does not require use of entropy or partition functions i.e. $g(f) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$.

One may construct a Kaniadakis entropy density S_d based on this equilibrium result using: $S_d = \int df \ln(g(f))$ When maximizing, one uses d/df which is the inverse function of $\int df$, so one obtains $\ln(g(f))$ back and equates it to an equilibrium result $-1/T(e-u)$. S_d integrated over phase space yields S which may be used in $E-TS + uN$. The result yields \ln of the grand partition function from which one may obtain E_{ave} by taking d/db $b=1/T$. A derivative related to d/dz yields $f(e_i)$ In this note, we try to show why this is the case. In doing so, it seems that changes in f are restricted to df/dT . Thus, one is really comparing $f(e_i/T1)$ with $f(e_i/T2)$ which is a "restricted" change.

We also consider possible issues with variations methods. For example, S_d Kaniadakis with the constraint $-(e-u)/T f$ yields an equation for f . One may also use $-g \ln(g) + (e-u)/T g$ to obtain

the same result. One, however, may not use $-g \ln(g) + (e-u)/T$ even though $(e-u)/T$ is a legitimate constraint. We argue that there is “physics”, namely the conservation of energy in elastic collisions behind the establishment of these entropy density variation approaches. In addition, the variational approaches may also be linked to the purely statistical $M!/(g(e_1)! g(e_2)! \dots)$ with Stirling’s approximation being used. We argue that the scattering approach maps into the statistical one. This has been considered in a separate note (2).

References

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